

ROADMAP FOR A SUSTAINABLE AND COMPETITIVE MARKET FOR OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHING

OpenAIRE

Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe

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Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe towards 2020

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A final report on the results of the APC pilot, containing recommendations drawn from the pilot, the economic study 'Towards a Competitive and Sustainable OA Market in Europe', and a consultation with stakeholders mapping a sustainable route for gold open access during the workshop 'On the road towards a sustainable open access publishing market' organised in The Hague on April 20th 2017.

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	Name	Organisation	Date
From	Gwen Franck Simone Sacchi Vasso Kalaitzi	LIBER	06/2018
Edited by	Gwen Franck	LIBER	
Reviewed by	Saskia De Vries Ilaria Fava Iryna Kuchma	SURF UGOE EIFL	
Approved by			
For delivery	Mike Chatzopoulos	UoA	

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Issue	Item	Reason for Change	Author	Organization
V0.1	Draft version	First draft based on workshop and economic study	Gwen Franck Saskia De Vries Simone Sacchi	LIBER SURF LIBER

V0.2	Final Version	Final version augmented with experiences from the final year of the Pilot (post-delivery date)	Gwen Franck	LIBER
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This roadmap identifies the key goals that Research Performing Organisations, Research Libraries and Funders should aim for in order to support a sustainable environment for open access publishing in the European Research Area, together with a range of suggested concrete actions that can be undertaken.

This Roadmap is partially based on the report ‘Towards a Competitive and Sustainable OA Market in Europe – A Study of the Open Access Market and Policy Environment’, which was published as deliverable D 5.3 in OpenAIRE2020 Workpackage 5 – better known as the FP7 Post-Grant Open Access Pilot. Additional suggestions and actions were crowdsourced during the workshop accompanying the end of the original Pilot period, augmented with elements gathered from the conclusions of the Pilot (final report available on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1304908>)

A fully transparent landscape

Monitoring:

Keep track of relative shares of author fees and subscription costs

Negotiation:

Do not accept non-disclosure clauses in contracts

Collaboration:

Engage with other institutions and funders to exchange knowledge

Simplification:

make author fee payment workflows uniform, predictable and transparent.

Do not agree with secrecy clauses when negotiating with publishers : publish the contracts so that author fees and subscription costs can be monitored and evaluated at institutional, national and European level.

Document author fee information in publication metadata and make it available as linked open data

Share good practices about negotiations in institutional and funder networks.

Do not accept ambiguity about journal status: clearly identify hybrid journals and do not make deals with publishers who are unclear about the status of their journals.

Impose strict conditions for funding author fees by setting a funding cap for reimbursement
Centralise and simplify author fee payment workflows at institutional or funder level.

All research outputs Open Access

Negotiation:

Ensure the right to self-archiving in institutional repository

Align:

Establish open science policies and align them with European Commission requirements

Training:

Researchers and staff in order to increase Open Science knowledge and skills

No open, no deal: no new deals without explicit permission for self-archiving in institutional repository
Support the flipping of subscription based journals to open access or to non-author fee based publishing platforms

Do not pay for author fees in hybrid journals: if these are not accompanied by an offsetting mechanism.

Align embargo periods and limit them to the internationally accepted limit of 6 months for STEM and 12 months for SSH. Do not engage in deals that impose longer embargoes.

The right to read is the right to mine: Do not engage in subscription deals that prevent TDM and other innovative research processes

Encourage authors to use open licenses and provide training in order to ensure that they are aware of all their options

Value open as essential element in scholarly lifecycle

Encouragement:

researchers to make their work open access at the moment of publication

Include

costs related to OA in research admin costs

Reward:

researchers who support Open Access e.g. by running a journal or platform

Acknowledge:

consider all types of research output for research evaluation, not just articles and monographs

'Open' is about outputs and workflows- value all activities that increase openness in the research lifecycle

Include 'open' in research evaluation: Do not consider research output that is not deposited in a repository.

Reward researchers for engaging in open access publishing initiatives such as running an open access journal.

Consider author fees as eligible costs in research grants.

Investigate in and apply alternative metrics who take into account openness

Establish open access policies and align them with other policies.

Train researchers and ensure they are aware of all open access options and their implications

Create a real market place for authors

Support infrastructure

Develop:
repository architecture and open access
publication platforms

Integration:
of open access repositories into existing CRIS

Support:
storage, sharing and archiving of of all types
of research output

Invest in Open Source repository infrastructure and consider sharing services in order to improve efficiency. Integrate and increase interoperability of repositories with CRIS

Support non-author fee based publishing platforms by hosting their infrastructure.

Look beyond the article: provide technical support to publish, evaluate and archive all types of scientific output in all stages of the research lifecycle

Provide infrastructure and invest in tools for text-and-data mining and other innovative research processes Support services who provide standards and persistent identifiers